

30 YEARS OF RELATIONS BETWEEN THE REPUBLIC OF KOREA AND THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6602572>

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Annotation: *Cooperation trends, issues of cooperation in political, trade-economic and cultural – humanitarian spheres are widely covered.*

Keywords: *Korea, Uzbekistan, foreign policy, cooperation, strategy*

South Korea is one of the 5 countries with a high share in foreign trade in Uzbekistan.

In particular, special emphasis is placed on the results of high-level meetings held over the past four years, the results of cooperation in New Directions and relations within the framework of international organizations. After gaining independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan became an equal member of the world community. In the foreign policy direction, the independent Uzbekistan emphasizes close cooperation with all countries of the rapidly developing world, as well as with the Republic of Korea.

The Republic of Korea was one of the first to recognize the independence of Uzbekistan, that is, at the end of 1991, diplomatic relations were established in 1992 in 29 janvar. Over the past 29 years, 17 high-level meetings have been held between the heads of State on both sides. In each of these meetings, the parties reached agreements, which are important for the development of political, trade-economic, cultural-humanitarian relations. In order to further strengthen the bilateral relations between Uzbekistan and the Republic of Korea, a joint declaration on strategic partnership was signed between the two countries in 2006.

In 2014, a joint declaration on the further development and deepening of the strategic partnership was signed. This document made it possible to raise the relations between the republics in the political, trade-economic, cultural-humanitarian spheres to a qualitatively new level.

Speaking about the political relations of the two countries, it is necessary to first emphasize the sincere friendship between the heads of State. This friendship

began the years when South Korean President Lee Myung-bak was the mayor of Seoul. In 2008, when Lee Myung-Bak won the presidential election and held the post of head of state, he invited the leader of Uzbekistan as an honorary guest to the inauguration ceremony. In May 2009, the leaders of Uzbekistan and South Korea met in Tashkent. Each meeting of the heads of State further strengthened the relations between the two countries.

Over the past four years, Uzbek-South Korean relations have reached a qualitatively new level based on rich and insightful political dialogue between the two leaders.

The total amount of government contracts and commercial contracts signed as a result of mutual state visits in 2017 and 2019 years amounted to 22 billion dollars. In 2019, the relations between our countries rose to the level of “Special Strategic Partnership”.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev took part in the second international forum on North Economic Cooperation held in the form of a video conference in Seoul on October 30, 2020 at the invitation of President of the Republic of Korea Moon Jae-in. In his speech, the head of our state stressed that such a multilateral dialogue in conditions of the difficult situation in the world and the global crisis creates an opportunity to effectively counteract new risks and threats and serves to ensure the stability, prosperity and consistent development of our countries.

In this regard, Shavkat Mirziyoyev touched upon the most important aspects of international policy and prospects for regional cooperation.

The proposal to continue joint work on the development of effective vaccines and membranes, systems for rapid and accurate diagnosis of diseases on the basis of the pharmaceutical cluster, which is organized in important areas, including in conjunction with Korean companies, was expressed.

The head of our state stressed that he sees the Republic of Korea as one of the key partners in bringing digital and “green” technologies to our country.

On January 28, 2021, president of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev held a meeting with the president of the Republic of Korea Mun Zhe-In in the form of a video conference.

The heads of state stressed the further strengthening of a special strategic partnership and comprehensive cooperation on bilateral relations. Current and prospective programs of cooperation in the fields of higher, vocational and preschool education, health care, digitization and restoration of cultural heritage objects were considered.

In the current year, it was announced that investments in the framework of the projects carried out with the participation of South Korean partners will be made up to 400 million dollars in total.

In addition, as a new direction of cooperation between the two countries, 55 new projects with a total value of more than 3.4 billion US dollars will be implemented in high-tech sectors, including Energy, oil and gas, chemical and petrochemical, pharmaceutical, processing industry, agriculture, infrastructure modernization, transport and logistics, tourism and many other sectors. To date, 14 rounds of political consultations have been held between the ministries of Foreign Affairs of the two countries (last held in the form of a video conference on November 5, 2020). On April 17-18, 2018, the minister of foreign affairs of the Republic of Korea, Jean-Yves, paid an official visit to Uzbekistan. Since November 2007, the annual Cooperation forum " Republic of Korea – Central Asia " has been functioning. In November 2020, the minister of Foreign Affairs A. Kamilov took part in the 13th meeting of the Forum.

The Republic of Korea occupies a leading position among the trade partners of the countries of the Asia-Pacific region of Uzbekistan. In particular, in accordance with the trade agreement signed in 1992, the most favorable regime of advantages was established between the countries. The fact that trade and economic relations between the two countries are growing year after year, the relations between the parties are characterized by the possession of a solid "foundation".

Today, Uzbekistan and Korea have completed 30 years of cooperation. Since the establishment of diplomatic relations, the Republic of Korea has become a tested and reliable strategic partner of Uzbekistan in all directions, especially in economic and social changes, international issues. In turn, establishing wide-ranging relations with Uzbekistan on political and economic fronts fully corresponds to the interests of the Korean side. Proceeding from this, the parties will try to further develop and strengthen their bilateral relations in the near and long term.

LIST OF LITERATURE

1. Rafał Lipniewicz " Tax administration and risk management in the digital age " 2017. 2. World bank "Risk-Based Tax Audits" 2011.
2. IMF working paper " Reducing Tax Evasion from Cross-Border Fraud: the role of digitization" 2019.

3. "Gazeta.uz" the speech of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the videoelectroject on July 16, 2020.